

EXPLORERS

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Florida Center for Cybersecurity

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University of South Florida is Florida's leading metropolitan research university. In 2018, USF skyrocketed into the top 25 public universities for research expenditures, becoming at the forefront of cutting-edge research of science and engineering.

The **Florida Center for Cybersecurity** (Cyber Florida) is a state-funded organization dedicated to positioning Florida as a national leader in cybersecurity through education and workforce development; innovative, interdisciplinary research; and community outreach. Hosted at the University of South Florida, Cyber Florida works with all 12 State University System of Florida (SUS) institutions as well as industry, government and defense to build partnerships and develop programs that grow and strengthen Florida's cybersecurity industry.

READY FOR:

x1 CHALLENGE

AI	Blockchain
Big Data	IoT
5G	Cybersecurity
Cloud/Edge	

RESEARCHERS

INNOVATORS

CHALLENGE #10 - USF-END-01

→ End-to-End Security In Multi-Domain Networks

Meet the expectations of this US Node through the technology challenge described below

DESCRIPTION

Ensuring end-to-end security In multi-domain networks has become necessary and important in enterprise computing. However, there is still a grand challenge on quantifying and measuring end-to-end security, as well as developing an efficient mechanism to ensure end-to-end security in multi-domain networks.

OBJECTIVES

Provide a solution to systematically address the above challenge by developing a strict mathematical foundation that can be tested and verified on experiments.

SKILLS REQUIRED

n/a

